

A STUDY OF VILAYAT KHAN'S SITTAR AND A R RAHMAN'S KEYBOARD AND THEIR CHILDHOOD EXPERIENCES AND SUFFERINGS

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Abstract:

The sixth string of Vilayat Khan one of the finest works of Namita Devidayal in this novel she has explored the biographical sketches of Ustad Vilayat Khan and his early life. He recorded his first 78 RPM disc at the age of 8 and gave his last concerts in 2004 at the age of 75. This book is chronicle of the journey of Ustad Vilayat Khan from a fatherless, adolescent to an immortal artist someone who impacted to his field both in aesthetics and practice. Vilayat was thought in the family style known as the Imdadkhani Gharna or Etawah Gharna after his father's death he under gone a lot of struggles in his life. Vilayat Khan was born into a family of tracing its pedigree generations back to the court musician of the Mughal rulers. The Mozart of Madras AR Rahman is a name to reckon as he has made India proud by winning two Oscars for his music in "Slumdog Millionaire". After his father's death and hardship of life, he started following his father's track and started his training in music under master Dhanraj. He got 50 as his first salary for operating a record player.

Key Words: Ustad, Imdadkhani Gharna, Etawah Gharna, Oscars

Namita Devidayal's book on Ustad Vilayat Khan is an interesting account of his life and musical journey. The book, The Sixth String of Vilayat Khan, has been authored by Namita Devidayal, who had earlier penned the bestseller, The Music Room: A Memoir. Namita says she has tried to create an impressionistic fluid portrait - of a magnificent artiste and a fragmented human being. "I have tried to imagine him and tell a story anchored in fact but narrated with poetic license, like improvising on a jazz standard. It would be a mistake to regard this strictly as a biography." The book is an outcome of Namita's long discussions with people who were close to the Ustad and his family and through interviews, archival records and photographs.

Vilayat Khan was 10 when his illustrious father Enayat Khan passed away, but not before inducting his son into the legacy of the greatest sitar gharana (his grandfather was Imdad Khan, who undertook the tough 40-day chilla ritual, when the musician does not step out of the house and only practises). Writing the life sketch of a legendary musician such as Ustad Vilayat Khan is no easy task. Going by his lineage, stature, proficiency and lasting influence, summing up his music and personality in 252 pages is like exploring a raga in five minutes. Yet, such an attempt is important to enable young musicians to imbibe from his distinctive style and virtuosity.

As a young lad, living in Calcutta, in a house named 'Riyaz,' Vilayat had only the sitar for a friend. He was eight when he performed at the All-India Bengal Music conference and earned immense praise. The Megaphone Recording Company even came up with a 78 rpm featuring the father on one side and the prodigious son, on the other. But his father's untimely death left Vilayat shattered, both monetarily and musically. The book gives a detailed account of how Vilayat fought hardships to become one of India's foremost musicians. One night, he left home with his sitar, swearing to return only as an accomplished musician. He boarded a train to Delhi and reached his destination thanks to kind-hearted ticket collectors. He went straight to All India Radio; the station director recognized him as Enayat Khan's son and gave him refuge in the station's garage. He used to have food from the canteen and clean instruments in the studio. He was delighted to see eminent artistes walking AIR's corridors and listen to the recordings of musical greats.

Packed with interesting anecdotes and providing insights into the artistic ambience of the time, the author takes the readers through Vilayat's training under his maternal grandfather (Bande Hasan Khan) and uncle (Zinda Hasan Khan), who were vocalists and would come to Delhi to teach him. Sometimes, Vilayat visited their house in Saharanpur.

Bande Hasan Khan was also a wrestler and took his grandson to the akhada to build his stamina. Vilayat's mother Basheeran Begum was happy that her family had undertaken the responsibility of his training, but her son's growing fondness for singing worried her. She warned him about breaking the family tradition. A distraught Vilayat approached his uncle, who advised him to make his sitar sing instead. So he began to consciously nurture the gayaki ang in his instrument. The Ustad, who was also an accomplished

surbahar player, once said, “When I sit down on stage to play, everything comes to me in the form of a vocal performance. It just happens.”

An entire chapter is devoted to the 1944 Vikramaditya Music Conference in Bombay, where a sitar maestro called Vilayat Khan was born. Soon he became a regular at prestigious festivals and private concerts. At the same time, another sitar exponent, Ravi Shankar was making a mark too. Though stories of their rivalry were spoken about in music circles, both had tremendous respect for each other. Vilayat’s tryst with fame, money and the film industry among his close friends were Naushad and Madan Mohan began when he moved to Bombay. It was also where he met his disciple Arvind Parikh, who came from a Gujarati business family. A devoted shagird, Arvindbhai also became his close confidante. By 1950, Vilayat Khan began touring the world.

His preparation for concerts included planning his attire. The book talks about how he would often have a dress rehearsal in which the entire family would be forced to participate. Even his silver and carefully-designed paan box had to be set the night before a performance. He loved the good life, traditional when it came to his art, while preferring to be up-to-date in his appearance. From Bombay, he moved to Shimla, to enjoy the quietude of the hills, and then to the U.S. While drawing the portrait of an older Vilayat Khan, Namita touches upon his uneasy relationship with his son Shujaat Khan, a well-known sitar player and his younger son Hidayat Khan’s struggle to live up to his father’s expectations. In 2004, after traversing the highs and lows of life like the notes of his strings, the Ustad died of lung cancer. In his hands, the sitar gained a beautiful voice. The greatest of musicians, an epoch maker, a visionary Vilayat was all that and much more. The contribution of player in field of sitar music has been myth. His sitar style is very well known and is being remembered with great respect. He has been widely acclaimed as the architect of modern sitar. Khan has mesmerized his audience with his magnificent Giyani and sitar Bhaj creating what is universally accepted as Vilayat Khan Bhaaj. No wonder he is the most influential instrumentalised of his era.

He got music learning from voted Enayat khan, Ustad Wahid khan, his maternal grandfather Banda Hussain Khan, Maternal Uncle Zinda Hussian Khan introduced a left hand technique where by continuing of a note for a much longer duration was achieved resulting lyrical and continuous flow in his music. Many rightly exclaimed that- His Sitar virtually sighs’ with matches balance between two hands he added different variety of crystal clear and elegant tears where is absent in his contemporary sitarists of other Gharanas. He has tremendous contribution in playing semi – classical, even folk music on sitar, and then in the only sitarist ti have the title, ‘Aftaab- A Sitar’ (Sun of Sitar) and Bhart Sitar Samrat (Emperor of Sitar).When of hear a taste for the good life. He smoked a pipe, loved bell room dancing and dranch pricing imported liquor, an acs theatre to the core of his being, he possemmed an expansive collection of vintage perfumes and exquisite iraninan carpets and played snooker and cards with the skull dugging of practiced con artist

Early Childhood Experiences and Sufferings of Vilayat Khan

One day afternoon Vilayat was sitting around with his friend and students when he called his son and he had got his school report card with zeros against almost every subject. Before showing it to his father the little boy had overwritten the numbers but the total marks more than a 100 percent. He asked his son whether he continues his studies or focus on music.

He said openly to his father ‘music abba’ he holding run going to school is very rare other than music. He said ‘Donkeys and genius will never see eye to eye’. And this boy will one day transform sound into colour and fragrance. Vilayat started his music practice form his father Enayat and waking him early in the morning, sometimes kicking him gently. Vilayat little finger cuts when he more played it would start bleeding. By his continues practice finger became hard like lead, gradually a musician was born. A year later Enayat student’s Bhupen Ghosh organized the All Bengal Music conference at modern theatre and Vilayat became the part of the programme when he eight year old boy played raga Bhairavi. For the next few days he was praised and blessing by all and said grand speculation about his future.

Enayat and Vilayat both of them have good time that time the mega phone recording company produced a 78 rpm in which the father played on one side and his son played on the other side, ragas Bhairavi and Todi soon they gained the popularity and Enayat where he ever went he took his son along with him But the joy was short lived. Enayat lived with that sweet and dangerous delusion that became his art had touched immortality. His life would as well. He was addicted by alcohollike imported whiskies and brandies which were available to him in the princely courts. He didn’t pay any attention to his health and doctor’s advice.

When he was at the Prayag music conference in Allahabad Where he continued drinking, vomited blood and fainted. When Vilayat 10 years old boy with him. He was terrified about his father’s health at that time someone said to him “you should save your father’s honor and play the sitar in his place” Vilayat heard the sound of mother’s wailing when he woke up around midnight. After his father’s death the house was a roar of silence before it had been only music and applause. Now it had lost his happiness the musical instrument was in a state of chronic tunelessness and dust settled on it. Young Vilayat started feeling aloof and more hopeless. When he was alive Enayat students, fans, patrons used to sit together in their home but when he was died everything evaporated like the hoggly mist. Apart from the material peril there was incoherent gloom that a child could sense.

Basherean Begum or Amma was thirty and beautiful lady hot sobbing about her husband's death but prayed vigorously she would often with full of rage insist his son to keep on practice the music. She said to him "Who do you think is going to support the family now? Are you going to cut grass or are you going to become a musician"? At the young age family burden fell on his shoulder. He woke up earlier in the morning to do his routine. Quite often he took the sitar and stood before his father's portrait and practiced the music. His mother stand behind the door, with full of tears and silently blessing his son. He is not like other boys. He stopped going out to play with friends as well. His world seemed to have come to an end. He was in dejected mood and growing through the album recollected all his past sweet experiences along with his father and grandfather, the picture was in white and black. He couldn't forget that day He said himself he couldn't believe that all this had been so cruelly snatched from him. Vilayat asked one of his Enayat's students to teach the music for him. But initially criticized him and asked to paid the dues. "Vailyat made lot of tricks to learn the music". Vilyat tried various methods to pursue music from him like woo him by pressing his feet, brought him opium, game cash but all the tricks became futile. Atlast Vilayat reached into his pocket, pulled out a pistol hold it to the musician's head and said 'will you teach me or do you want to die' in order he extracted what he wanted.

Basherean Begum realized that her son was prodigiously gifted and took more musical training continued with the vigour and his level of proficiency made like his fore fathers. She surely is known that blind practice is insufficient, to require more practice in order to make as a mature musician. He slipped out of the home with a small amount and then started his musical train journey and reached old Delhi where he found that recently established AIR and met Bukhari who was the fan of his father's music.

Bhukari adopted the young Vilayat, allowing him to live in the tin roofed garage next to the radio canteen where he practiced his music in a room at the station. He was given odd jobs like cleaning and tuning the tampuras. He took food from the radio station canteen only after he had finished his daily practice. The radio station became one of the surrogate teachers that the teenaged Vilayat would adopt over the next few years. He had no father and teacher to guide him, Vilayat became observed with intensively to the 78 rpm records of past musicians, especially vocalists. He spent hours listening to Abdul Karim Khan, Abdul Wahid Khan, Faiyaz Khan, Zohrabai Agrawal and later Kesarbai Kerker. He learned their music by heart, each note and phrase and pause. Though he had no formal education he had a photographic aural memory and his mental spoils were certainly active.

The musicologist Deepak Raja, Who has analyzed Vilayat's music extensively, suggests that this extraordinary quality revealed itself in his music throughout his life. One day vilayat with full courage said to a senior vocalist "Khansahib please can I take ten compositions from you"? He sarcastically said to him , "Why ten? Take hundred", mashallah. But he asked him in return, "you have to bring an many keema parathas for us all to share tomorrow". As a fatherless and ambitious Vilayat attached himself to a variety of mentors who became solid rocks in his life. Joshi babu was as erudite musician from Lucknow who spoke English, Urdu and played sitar and fan of Enayat. He has always referred Joshi as his first son. After Enayat's Death, Joshi sent a message to Vilayat, "I have some of your family wealth, so please come and take it from, me whenever you are needy". Vilayat viewed Joshi babu as an elder brother and teacher, but Joshi looked upto him equally because Vilayat was his Guru's Son and therefore the Gharna's Khalifa or head. The teenaged Vilayat Khan's musical training was taken over by his grandfather Bande Hasan Khan and his beloved mamu, Zinda Hasan Khan. There two men oxygenated Vilayat's world again but they were singer not sitar player. As he grew older, Vilayat started playing small concerts here and there to earn some money but this was insufficient to run the family.

Vilayat shared his personal experiences and pains of his life once he was invited by local daroga or inspector where he performs the music as his fees he got only slap on his cheeks received from inspector. This was the bitter experience of vilayat at his early stage. Later he had been invited by business home where he perform the music before he went for playing the music the host asked him to join them for dinner.

On the dining table Haleem and Briyani Variety of vegetables kept, though he was starving he denied politely after the performance Vialyat received his fees and rush to eat his fascinated food Karim. He learnt music from his father's brother Wahid khan who had modern name for himself as a master of Surabar. Anokhalal Mishra was astonished the tabla player Banaras who was known for his own speed instrument and pyrotechnics of Vilayat. He said, "Where has this bhoot, this Ghost come from? He is definitely not human". He had decided he would only return as a maestro. After his father's death the whole family plunge into the gloominess. Basherun Begum was a wife of Enayat and mother of Vilayat. Who was 30 years old still she was more gorgeous, she was much worried about her son become a vocal singer. So, she insisted him to practice the sitar music. No one could take care of the family burden she asked her son "who do you think is going to support the family now?". Vliayat learned music from various musicians while he was undergone lot of hurdles and sufferings.

A R Rahman:

Allah Rakha Rahman was born as A. S. Dileep Kumar in Madras, Tamil Nadu, on 6 January 1967. His father, R. K. Shekhar from a Mudaliar family, was a film-score composer and conductor for Tamil and Malayalam films. Rahman began studying piano at age four. He assisted his father in the studio, playing the

keyboard. After his father's death when Rahman was nine years old, the rental of his father's musical equipment provided his family's income. Raised by his mother, Kareema (born Kashturi), Rahman, who was studying in Padma Seshadri Bala Bhavan had to work to support his family. which led to him to routinely miss classes and fail exams. Therefore, the Principal Rajalakshmi Parthasarathy summoned Rahman and his mother and told them that Rahman should focus on academics irrespective of family circumstances. However, in an interview in 2012, Rahman said that his mother was summoned and was told to take him to the streets of Kodambakkam to beg and not to send him to the school anymore.

Rahman attended another school called MCN for a year, and later joined the Madras Christian College Higher Secondary School, where he was admitted on his music talent and formed a band with his high school classmates. However, after discussing with his mother, he later dropped out of school to pursue a career as a full-time musician.

Rahman was a keyboard player and arranger for bands such as Roots (with childhood friend and percussionist Sivamani, John Anthony, Suresh Peters, JoJo and Raja) and founded the Chennai-based rock group Nemesis Avenue. He mastered the keyboard, piano, synthesizer, harmonium and guitar, and was particularly interested in the synthesizer because it was the "ideal combination of music and technology". Rahman began his early musical training under Master Dhanraj, and at age 11 began playing in the orchestra of Malayalam composer (and close friend of his father) M. K. Arjunan. He soon began working with other composers, such as M. S. Viswanathan, Vijaya Bhaskar, Ilaiyaraaja, Ramesh Naidu, Vijay Anand, Hamsalekha and Raj-Koti, accompanied Zakir Hussain, Kunnakudi Vaidyanathan and L. Shankar on world tours and obtained a scholarship from Trinity College London to the Trinity College of Music. During his early career, Rahman had assisted many music directors to play keyboard and synthesizer. One of the notable works includes a Malayalam film, Ramji Rao Speaking released in 1989 where Rahman and Sivamani programmed a song called "Kalikalam" for the music director S.Balakrishnan. Studying in Madras, Rahman graduated with a diploma in Western classical music from the school.

Rahman was introduced to Qadiri tariqa when his younger sister was seriously ill in 1984. His mother was a practising Hindu. At the age of 23, he converted to Islam with other members of his family in 1989, changing his name to Allah Rakha Rahman (A. R. Rahman). A.R.Rahman needs no introduction. He is the man who has redefined contemporary Indian music and left an indelible mark on the global music scene. He is a prolific composer, Singer and Song Writers who have had numerous awards and accolades under his portfolio. Rahman is best known for his innovative style of blending Indian classical music with electronic music. He predominantly works in Tamil and Hindi films. He rose to international fame with his academy awards winning sound track for the movie slumdog millionaire which showcased his versatility of mastering of various musical genres. Rahman has won several prestigious awards, including six national film awards, two academy awards, two Grammy awards and a BAFTA award. His music continues to inspire and enchant audiences worldwide. Rahman is skilled in Carnatic music, Western Classical, Hindustani Music and the Qawwadi style, Symphonic Orchestral themes have accompanied his scores. When he has employed leitmotif.

His composition, Orchestration and the human voice, evolving Indian pop music with unique timbres, forms and instrumentation. AR is arguably more adept at using synthesized sound and brass in his music and his music has gained wider national (India) International popularity. However many critics, much enthusiasts consider him to be one of the greatest musicians in the world and have compared him to the likes of Beethoven, Mozart and other legendary musicians from different parts of the world. AR Rahman born as A.S.Dileep Kumar, is known for his exceptional musical skills and innovative approach to composition. Hence are some key aspects of his music skills. Rahman is a masterful composer who has the ability to create music across various genres and styles. He has composed music for a wide range of films, incorporating elements of Indian classical music, Western Classical music, electronic music, world music and more. His compositions are often characterized by their intricate melodies, rich harmonies and seamless fusion of different musical influences. Rahman's expertise in arrangement is evident in his ability to create intricate and layered musical arrangements. He skillfully combines different instruments, voices and sounds to create a unique sonic landscape for his compositions. His arrangements often feature a blend of traditional Indian instruments, orchestral elements, electronic beats and modern production techniques. Rahman is proficient in playing various musical instruments.

He is known to play the piano, Keyboard, Guitar, flute, and many traditional Indian instruments like the tabla, veena and santoor. His understanding of different instruments enables him to create diverse and captivating musical textures in his compositions. In addition to composing, AR is also a talented singer. He has lent his voice to many of his compositions, delivering emotionally charged performances. His voice has a distinct quality and he is known for his ability to convey the emotions of a song with great depth and expression. AR Rahman is known for embracing technology in his music production. He was one of the pioneers of using digital music production techniques in the Indian Film Industry. He integrates electronics elements and sound design assembling into his composition, creating a modern and innovative sound. Rahman is constantly pursuing boundaries and exploring new musical territories to experiment with different genres, sounds and production techniques this experimental approach has earned him international recognition and has made him a

trailblazer in the Indian music industry. Overall AR Rahman's music skills encompass composition, arrangements instrumentation, vocals, technological expertise and a spirit of experimentation. His ability to blend diverse musical influences and create music that resonates with a global audience is a testament to his exceptional talent and artistry.

AR Rahman's father was his first music teacher, training him in playing various instruments like piano, harmonium and guitar. This early training in multiple instruments, provided him with a strong foundation in music theory, composition and arrangement is also equipped him with the ability to experiment with different sounds and features in his composition.

AR Rahman's upbringing in a Tamil speaking Muslim family with a background in Sufi music, added a unique cultural and religious dimension to his music. Sufi music's spiritual and emotional elements resonated with Rahman and found their way into his compositions, infusing them with a sense of depth and soulfulness. During his formative years as a musician Rahman witnessed the advent of digital music technology. This exposure to new technological advancements in music production, synthesis and sound designs allowed him to incorporate electronic elements and equipment with innovative sounds in his compositions. He embraced technology as a tool for creative expression, resulting in a contemporary and cutting-edge sound in his music. Overall AR Rahman's early exposure to diverse musical genres, his training in traditional and contemporary music, his cultural and religious influences and his access to new technologies all played a significant role in shaping his unique music style. His ability to blend different musical elements, create captivating melodies and experiment with sound textures set him apart and established him as a pioneer in the Indian music industry.

Early Childhood Experiences and sufferings of AR Rahman:

AR Rahman became a sole breadwinner of his family after his father passed away at a very young age. Oscar-Winner AR Rahman lost his father R.K. Shekar when he was just nine. Shekar was a popular musician and music conductor who worked with some of the leading composers of South cinema. He died in the prime of his life but it is the good will that he left behind for his family that became a stepping stone for AR Rahman during the early days of his music career. AR Rahman excelled at seeing his father suffering from an illness was the darkest phase of his life 'My childhood was not a normal one it was a little secluded I mainly lived in hospital with my father getting treatment and at the age of 11 or 12 I started working. I didn't have the privilege of going out or playing sports. But I had personal time, which I spent mostly with music. Which is in a way was a blessing'. He said during an interview. He also noted that he tries not to revisit the memories from the time when his father was ill. One day, he was pulled out from the middle of a class at school and had to get back home about four years until he passed away in 1976. Rahman was in the 4th standard. I can still remember me cremating him setting him on fire. I was as young as nine and that is one image in my life never goes off. That memory still hurts me but it makes me understand life better because it all happened at very early stages on my life.

It has given me something a normal kid could never have had, he said after the passing away of his father, the responsibility of running the family fell on the young shoulders of AR Rahman. He had to discontinue his school, so he could work full time to support his family of five. He began running out his father's music equipments before his father's long time collaborator and late music composer M.K. Arjunan helped him kick start his music career. He started at the bottom of the ladder earning Rs.50 for his first salary. He became a session musician and a keyboard player and gradually progressed to compose jingles for television advertisements before he landed his first feature film assignment *Roja*.

Difference between Vilayat and A R Rahman:

Both are undoubtedly pioneers of the Indian music industry who share a common passion for creating soulful and memorable music. Vilayat is known for his experimental and innovative approach to music, which involves the use of Sitar in the Indian classical music. Rahman's music involves a fusion of traditional Indian Music with electronic and world music elements. Vilayat who was awarded a Padma Shri and Padma Bhushan in 1964 and 1968 respectively, refused to accept them for rather different reasons. He is known as God of Music. AR Rahman has achieved international recognition.

Rahman has won the Oscar for original score and original song in Danny Boyle's *Slumdog Millionaire* in 2009 and nominated for the Best original score for *127 Hours* in 2011. Vilayat has a tremendous following in India and some parts of the world. While Vilayat and AR Rahman have different styles and approaches to music, they both have a common passion for creating soulful and memorable melodies. Their contribution to the Indian music industry has been immense and they continue to inspire generations of musicians and music lovers alike.

Vilayat is a veteran composer who started his career at the age of 8 and gave his last concert in 2004 at the age of 75. AR Rahman on the other hand, is a relatively newer entrant to the music industry. He gained fame with his debut sound track for the movie *Roja* in 1992, and has since then become a household name in the Indian music industry. AR Rahman is also known as the God of music for his versatility and mastery in various musical genres.

In Islam Allah is referred to as A.R. Rahman which means 'The Most Gracious' this is one of the most common names used to describe Allah in the Quran, which is the holy scripture of Islam. It is a reminder for Muslims to approach Allah with humility, gratitude and love. Ya Rahman is an Arabic phrase commonly used in

Islamic prayers and supplications. It is derived from the Arabic name for God, A.R.Rahman which means the most Gracious. 'Ya' is an Arabic word used to call upon someone or address them directly.

Both are legendary musical maestros and highly talented who have made a great mark in the Indian music industry. Both have their unique styles and approaches to music, and their work have got a national recognition by critics and people alike. Vilayat Khan and AR Rahman both are Muslims. AR Rahman is a converted Muslim but Vilayat Khan was directly descended from Muslim family. Both are dropped out from the school. Vilayat Khan was not at all interested to go to school. One of the reason was that who obtained very the lowest marks in all his subjects.

According to AR Rahman after his father's death he couldn't pay the school fees. So He unable to pay the school fees. So he was forced into drop out his school education. Both are consider as the god of music. Both are faced various hurdles and obstacles on the way of their musical journey.

Both are received lot of award in their life. AR Rahman is the worldwide recognized Oscar award for his music. Both are consider their father as the first music teacher. So they learnt the music from their father. Vilayat Khan and A R Rahman are two of the legendary and most prolific music composers of the Indian music industry. Their contributions to the Indian music industry have been immense and they contribute to inspire generations of musicians and music lovers alike. Besides there are some notable differences between the two music maestros.

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